

Religion, Rationality and Bollywood

Dr. Rajesh Kumar *

Abstract

How do religion and emotion knowledge intersects through Hindi cinema, popularly referred to as Bollywood, is the subject of inquiry of this paper. This paper contrasts the notions of religious emotions and secular emotions and posits that Bollywood is promoting rationality in religion by portraying secular emotions in its films. It is often said that religion, Bollywood and the game of cricket are the three shapers of modern Indian society. This paper tries to correlate religion and Bollywood to understand how Hindi films are inculcating the element of rationality by converting the religious emotion into secular emotion.

This paper undertakes three research questions. First, what is the role of Bollywood in shaping religious emotions in India? Second, how Bollywood is introducing a strand of rationality and secularism in religious emotions in India? Third, how Bollywood can play an even important role in Indian society by inculcating rationality in religious emotions?

For answering these three questions, this paper undertakes the case studies of two Bollywood films—*Oh My God* (2012) and *PK* (2014). The content of both movies constitute the key source for this paper. Both movies, with English subtitles, are available on various websites like YouTube and streaming services like Netflix. This paper applies the methodologies of semiotics, narratology and discourse analysis to analyze the messages given in *PK* and *Oh My God*.

This paper posits that Bollywood is one of the most important shapers of religious emotions in India.¹ Indians are avid filmgoers and consequently India is the largest filmmaking country in the world. Its revenues are only second to Hollywood. Bollywood wields a tremendous cultural influence in India. People perceive various aspects of their lives through Bollywood cinema. As a result, religious emotions are also greatly influenced by Hindi films. In response to second question, as mentioned earlier, this paper undertakes the case study of *Oh My God* and *PK* and portends that although there has been no dearth of patriarchal, jingoistic and theologically regressive cinema, but overall Bollywood gives the message of a rational religion, whose principles are same for all faiths.² Bollywood preaches the values of religious brotherhood and harmony. Bollywood discards superstitions and encourages a scientific attitude towards religion. Although, India is a Hindu dominated country, but Bollywood has never shied away from taking negative points of Hinduism head on. But that also does not mean that Bollywood spares other religions such as Islam, Sikhism and Christianity. Bollywood gives the clear message that the essence of all religions is same. There is only one God and he is same for all religions. Bollywood is especially against godmen or religious gurus who present themselves as the official representative of God on this earth. According to Bollywood, these religious gurus are responsible for most of the evils related to religion in India. Case studies of *Oh My God* and *PK* result in thought provoking conclusions regarding religious emotions.

A Content Analysis of Oh My God

In *Oh My God*, Kanji Bhai, a shop owner sues God in the court because his shop was gutted in an earthquake and insurance company claims that since it was an act of God, the company is not responsible for claims. Religious gurus become the respondents in the case and film presents these godmen as caricatures. Kanji Bhai challenges the conventional assumptions of organized religion and asks religious gurus that since they are representatives of God, they should pay for his claim. In an interesting turn of events, God himself comes to Kanji Bhai to help him albeit dressed as a modern man. Kanji Bhai does not recognize him as God and assumes him as a well-wisher and a friend. God tells Kanji Bhai to use religious books to find answers to the questions posed by godmen. People start supporting Kanji Bhai's movement. Kanji Bhai gets a paralysis attack and is hospitalized. Godmen capitalize on Kanji Bhai's situation and declare him the avatar of God who came to earth to preach

* Associate Professor Department of Political Science PPN College Kanpur

real sense of religion. They declare a date when plug from his life support system will be switched off. God appears by the bedside of Kanji Bhai and brings him back to consciousness. This time God appears as the religion portray him and says to Kanji Bhai, now you can recognize me. God says that I don't need places of worship and I am least interested in offerings made to me. I have my own house and these offerings should be given to poor people. Kanji Bhai goes out and scolds people for making him God and starts breaking his own statues and asks people not to go to Godmen. God disappears and his voice tells Kanji Bhai not to search for him because he is everywhere.

The film has interesting scenes from which inferences can be drawn about religious emotions.³ In the film, Kanji Bhai sells the statues of Gods as a business. In a telling comment, he says that as long as people keep on playing with these toys, his business will keep on flourishing. A Muslim asks him to take care of his shop while he wants to go for a pilgrimage. Kanji Bhai scolds him and says that instead of going to pilgrimage, he should have his shop repaired. A Muslim lawyer who helps Kanji Bhai in preparing his case, says, religion has been created for men, men have not been created for religion. Kanji Bhai makes fun of godmen by saying that if you pay more money, there is a smaller queue for entering into temple, while poor have to be in queue for longer period. He produces receipts of giving money for various temples in the court and says that he has paid the premium in various temples. He accuses godmen of taking franchise of God. He alleges godmen of being salesmen of God. In a TV interview, Kanji Bhai says that religion is the business of fear. Godmen tell people that if you commit sins, you will become dog in next life or you will go to hell and will be fried in hot oil. He tells godmen fearlessly that you people have converted God into a business brand. When in hospital God appears before him in his traditional form, God tells him that I have appeared in my traditional form so you can believe in me. But I am not like that. Because of my calendars, pictures, movies and scriptures people believe that I appear like that. God jokingly comments that his latest picture has not been uploaded on Facebook. God says that I am everybody's friend but nobody believes this fact. I have enough common sense to understand that making offerings to me is of no use. I am interested in people's faith. God says that people come to me only for their selfish reasons. They come with strange exchange offers. If I pass the examination, I will make a long walk to the temple. If my girlfriend says yes for marriage, I will light candles in church. And even people, who for whatever reasons, cannot come to me, blame me that I have not called them. God asks what should I do? Should I send them invitation letters? Kanji Bhai asks God that when you are aware of all this, then why don't you end this. God responds that I have not asked anybody to construct temples for me. I have only created human beings. It is human beings who have created caste and religion. When Kanji Bhai humiliates Godmen badly, one of them says that people you see here are not God loving but God fearing. You might humiliate us now but they will come back to us. In the end when God disappears and Kanji Bhai looks for him, a voice tells him that don't look for me. I am in the rains, which are falling on fields. I am with birds and making nests with them. I am lunching with ants.

A Content Analysis of PK

In PK, an alien comes earth to study human beings. But his remote control is snatched away by a hoodlum. Now his problem is that without that remote control he cannot call the spaceship back to take him to his own planet. He starts trying to understand the culture of earth. Since his acts appear to be crazy, people start calling him PK, which literally means a drunkard. He is told by various people that only God can help him. He starts going from one religious place to another but gets confused regarding how can there may be so many different Gods with different infrastructure and different methodologies to please them. Jaggu, the lead female protagonist, works for a TV channel and is tired of doing mindless stories. Both meet and realize that Tapaswi ji, a Godman, is their common enemy. PK's remote is with him and he tells people that it is the part of Lord Shiva's musical instrument while Jaggu's family members are staunch disciples of Tapaswi ji and she is sick of godman's interference in her family matters. The owner of channel also dislikes Tapaswi ji, because once he had done a news story on godman and his disciples had beaten him up. They organize a debate between PK and Tapaswi ji. Godman loses and is forced to give the remote back to PK. Thus PK finds his way back home but prior to that he unites heroine with her lover who had been separated due to a misunderstanding. Jaggu is a Hindu while her lover is shown to be a Pakistani Muslim. Thus film tackles the religious prejudices against Muslims also in its storyline. Tapaswi ji makes insulting

comments about Muslims and warns Jaggu that his lover will not marry him. PK proves Tapswi ji wrong by proving that Jaggu's lover had not deceived her. In entire film Tapaswi ji is presented as a caricature and fraud who fools people by pretending that he has a direct connection to God.

PK makes some startling, yet true, comments about different religions.⁴ Jaggu elaborates how by online worship and offerings, Tapaswi ji has used technology to strengthen his business empire. PK is shown to be seeing the religious world without any preconceived notions since he is an alien. He finds people's attitude regarding religion and God completely illogical. He says that there are many Gods on this earth. Every God has his own company, which people call religion. In a touching scene he goes to hospital and examines naked kids to see whether various Gods have stamped them to prove which particular religion they belong to. When Tapaswi ji tells a person to go to a temple in Himalaya's glacier to have his problem solved, PK challenges him by saying that if a kid comes to his father with a problem, then father would help him or suggest him to travel 2000 kilo meters to go to another temple and tell his problem to God's statue there. PK says that religion is the business of fear. He gives a live example by putting a stone in front of a college where exams are being held. Students, afraid of exams, come and touch the stone reverently and put money there. In the story when people become aware about the duplicity of godmen, a Muslim girl child asks that my friends want to go to the school, but there is a *fatwa* (religious decree) that if girls go to the school, they will be shot. Girl child says that our God can't be that petty that he will object to our going to school. Film tackles the issue of religious conversions also, which is an important political and religious issue in India. A tribal says that missionaries tell me that I should convert to Christianity; otherwise I will go to hell. He says further I want to ask, had God wanted me to be Christian, would I not have been borne in a Christian family. In the film, there is a terror attack in which PK's friend dies. Perpetrators' message says that they will protect their religion. In the TV show Tapaswi ji says that he will protect his God from attacks from people like PK. PK connects Islamic terror act with Tapaswi ji's proclamation and says that there are literally billions of planets in this universe and you people while sitting in a small planet, in a small place proclaim that you will protect the God? God does not need your protection. You need the protection of God. Answering Tapaswi ji's question, PK says there are two Gods. One who created us and the other who was created by religion and godmen. We should believe in the God who made us and do away with the duplicate Gods created by various religions. In the last scene, in a remarkable comment PK tells his friends from his planet about earthlings that when these people make love, they hide but when they want to have fights, they do it in front of everybody. There is a great difference in what these people say and do. One year later, PK leads the research team from his planet to understand the duplicity of earthling

Messages of *Oh My God* and *PK*

In spite of the fact that *Oh My God* and *PK* are very different films, there are notable similarities about their messages regarding religious emotions.⁵ One needs to keep in mind that these films did not belong to avant-garde or offbeat category. These were films of commercial mainstream and profit motive was very much there. Films gave touching messages regarding religion but without compromising with entertainment value. *Oh My God* had Akshay Kumar, one of the most bankable actors of Bollywood, as protagonist, while *PK* had Aamir Khan, one of the finest actors and stars, as lead actor. Both films had very hummable songs, which are a prime condition for a hit Bollywood film, and both films had a technical finesse about them. The argument is that makers of the films struck a fine balance between entertainment and messages regarding religion. Religious fundamentalist disliked both films and screenings of the films were disrupted at many places. Both films had to face legal challenges as well. But since India is a thriving democracy with very strong right to free expression and has a very conscientious judiciary, these factors did not have any serious effects for profitability of films and even viewers did not have any problems in going to theaters and enjoying the films.

In spite of very different storylines, both films had a common message running through their themes. For instance both films say that God is not to be found in temples, mosques or Churches. This message especially resonates with Indian viewers because of Ram Janmbhoomi and Babari Mosque controversy that has been raking Indian political and social life from last thirty years. Hindu's believe that their revered God Rama was borne in Ayodhya while Muslims believe that it is the site of Babari mosque built by their ancestor Babar. Both Hindu and Muslim community claim

this site as their own. Indian Supreme Court has given the verdict that the site belongs to Hindus. But court's judgment was based upon solid legal reasoning and not on religious arguments. This controversy does not find direct mention in either *PK* or *Oh My God*, but scene after scene and dialogue after dialogue exhort viewers to understand that it is the God who had created the world and he does not need a house built by fanatic masses.

Apart from this also, there are many common messages given by both films. *PK* and *Oh My God* poignantly show how religious gurus control the religion. Religion has become a profit making industry. People blindly follow religious gurus and superstitions promoted by them. Godmen have exploited people's religious emotions and have become business tycoon. Modern religion is run like a well-organized company. People waste their energy and resources by going to these gurus. The resources they waste as offerings in religious places should be given to poor and needy people. That will make God really happy. There may be many religions but there is only one God. God created men but men created religion. Both films, especially *Oh My God*, have a Marxist message also that religion is like opium given to the people, which stops them from thinking rationally. Both films very strongly convey the message that instead of walking on paths shown by traditional religion, people should use their own rational thinking to decide what is right and wrong in modern context. A contrast between religious emotion and secular emotions, clearly tell people to embrace secular emotions.

What More Bollywood could do

Now we come to the question, how Bollywood can play an even more important role in inculcating rationality in Indian society?⁶ One thing that becomes clear by the content analysis by both films that the message has to be given in an entertaining manner. Thus there should be more films about promoting rational thought, education, women's and child rights but these ideas should be woven in the themes of entertainment. An analysis of the films of previous decades show that Indian people do not like cinema which is preachy and ostensibly message oriented. The art is to challenge dogma without making people feel that it is an attack on their religion. That is why in order to target religious dogma; both films use the strategy of making godmen the symbol of dogmatic belief system and attack them, so viewers can absorb the message without having their religious sensibilities hurt. Yet, there should be no dumbing down and viewers' intelligence should not be insulted. Filmmakers should be clear that they should challenge traditional religion but they should do it smartly without hurting the religious sentiments of the people. Treading this fine line is the biggest challenge for the filmmakers. Judiciary and government should support when a theocratic minority invariably attacks such cinema. Indian government offers awards to the best of cinema every year. The government can announce a special award for a film that promotes rational thought regarding religion. In similar manner, there are various private organizations such as Filmfare and Stardust, which offer awards to the best of cinema every year. They can also announce a special category for films promoting rational thought. Print, electronic and social media should be in general more supportive of such cinema.

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